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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20544068>**Abstract**

The article discusses the third Mongol campaign led by Hulagu Khan in the 1250s and the extensive damage suffered by Nakhchivan, like other occupied regions of Azerbaijan, during this invasion. It is noted that one of the most important territories of the Ilkhanate, established in 1256, was Azerbaijan. However, following the death of Hulagu Khan, the central authority within the state weakened to some extent. The rulers of the Golden Horde located to the north, attempted to take advantage of this situation. During these invasions, it was primarily the Azerbaijani population, as well as towns and villages, that suffered devastation. Both sides plundered the inhabitants, destroyed settlements, and laid waste to agricultural lands and orchards in several Azerbaijani regions, including Nakhchivan. Toward the end of the thirteenth century, the situation began to stabilize to a certain extent. Nakhchivan was partially restored following the reforms implemented by Ghazan Khan. Nevertheless, after his reign, renewed internal conflicts and the oppression of the Chobanid emirs once again placed the region in a difficult condition. These wars caused extensive destruction in Nakhchivan. It is therefore not coincidental that foreign travelers and historians who visited the region in subsequent centuries frequently referred to the devastation inflicted upon it by the Mongols.

Keywords: Ilkhanate, Nakhchivan, reform, occupation, political situation

Despite the Mongol conquest of the Near East, the South Caucasus, and Asia Minor during the 1220s and 1230s, a number of major feudal principalities in these regions had still retained their independence by the middle of the thirteenth century. In 1251, the Great Mongol Khan Möngke, a grandson of Genghis Khan, decided to complete the conquest by dispatching a Mongol military expedition under the command of Hulagu Khan to these territories. For this purpose, the rulers of the four uluses were ordered to allocate two out of every ten warriors to Hulagu Khan's campaign force. Military preparations were completed within two years. In 1253, an army of approximately 120,000 troops under Hulagu Khan was sent to the Near East [4]. The principal objective of this campaign was to subjugate the independent rulers of Iran, Arab Iraq, Syria, and other provinces. To achieve this aim, Hulagu Khan secured the support of major feudal lords, subordinated numerous local rulers, captured large cities, and seized substantial booty. In 1256, the Nizari Ismaili stronghold of Alamut in northern Iran was overthrown. In 1257, Azerbaijan was brought under Mongol control. In February 1258, Hulagu Khan captured Baghdad, thereby bringing an end to the Abbasid Caliphate, which had existed for more than five centuries (750–1258) [4]. In the same year, Nakhchivan also came under Hulaguid rule. As a result of these newly conquered territories, the fifth Mongol ulus—the state of the Hulaguids (Ilkhanids)—was established.

The Ilkhanate, which existed for approximately one hundred years following its establishment until 1357, exerted a profound influence on the socio-political, economic, and cultural life of Azerbaijan. Significant changes occurred within its territorial boundaries,

the ethnic composition of its population, religious beliefs, culture, and language [2, p. 19].

Azerbaijan consistently occupied a leading position in the political, socio-economic, and cultural life of the Ilkhanid state. For this reason, cities such as Maragheh, Tabriz, and Soltaniyeh served at different times as capitals of the state. Between 1256 and 1265, Maragheh functioned as the capital; from 1265 to 1304, Tabriz assumed this role; between 1304 and 1316, Soltaniyeh became the principal administrative center; and from 1316 to 1357, Tabriz once again played a central role in the administration of the state [27, p. 69].

Nakhchivan in the Administrative-Territorial Division of the Ilkhanid State. The territory of the Ilkhanate extended from Derbent to the Persian Gulf, and from the borders of Egypt to the Amu Darya. According to its administrative-territorial organization, the state was divided into vilayets (provinces), the provinces into eyalets (administrative districts), and these, in turn, into tumens. One of these provinces was Azerbaijan [11, pp. 78–79]. As a province, the borders of Azerbaijan extended from the Caspian Sea through the province of Gilan, south of the cities of Zanjan, Savojbolagh, and Ushnu, as well as the fortress of Ruyindiz; west of the cities of Urmia, Salmas, Khoy, Maku, and Nakhchivan; from the city of Dvin; along Lake Goycha and the Debed River; west and north of the province of Sheki; and north of the city of Derbent [10, p. 233]. The province of Azerbaijan was divided into four eyalets: Azerbaijan, Mughan, Arran, and Shirvan. Although the eyalet named Azerbaijan mainly comprised the territories south of the Aras River, Nakhchivan—which geographically belonged to the region of Arran—was administratively incorporated into the Azerbaijan eyalet under Ilkhanid territorial

division. The Azerbaijan eyalet was further divided into nine tumens. The historian Hamdallah Mustawfi (1282–1345) referred to eight of these tumens: Tabriz, Ardabil, Pishkin, Khoy, Sarab, Maragha, Marand, and Nakhchivan [22, p. 37]. From 1258 onward, the territory of Nakhchivan acquired the status of a distinct tumen within the Ilkhanid state [19, p. 69].

At that time, the multifaceted term “tumen” was primarily used in military, administrative, and monetary contexts. Militarily, it referred to a unit consisting of ten thousand warriors; monetarily, it denoted a value equal to ten thousand dinars; and administratively, it designated a territorial unit capable of supplying ten thousand soldiers [14, p. 97]. Thus, the granting of tumen status to Nakhchivan indicates that it encompassed a vast territory.

Situated in the northwestern part of the Azerbaijan eyalet, the Nakhchivan tumen covered a territory larger than the present-day borders of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, including certain lands on the southern banks of the Aras River. According to the accounts of Hamdallah Mustawfi, five of the twenty-seven cities of Azerbaijan at that time belonged to the Nakhchivan tumen: Nakhchivan, Ordubad, Azad, Anjan, and Maku [22, p. 51]. This tumen extended over a broad territory from Maku to the Qafan Mountains [14, p. 96]. To the north and east, it bordered the eyalet of Arran. The frontier with Arran began south of Lake Goycha and extended southeastward, passing north of Shahbuz and northeast of Qafan and the Hekari River. To the southeast and south, the Nakhchivan tumen bordered the Khoy and Marand tumens of the Azerbaijan eyalet. The boundary with the Marand tumen followed the course of the Aras River. South of the river, the border extended from the direction of Julfa toward the south, while the territory of Maku remained within the Nakhchivan tumen. The boundary with the Khoy tumen passed north of the city bearing the same name. To the west, the borders began in the territories east of Lake Van and stretched northward, passing west of the Surmali plain and the city of Dvin [7, p. 47]. Consequently, the southern boundaries of the Nakhchivan tumen also included the city of Maku and its surrounding territories south of the Aras River. The fact that Maku-located not far from Nakhchivan and on approximately the same latitude—was not assigned to other Azerbaijani tumens, particularly the neighboring tumens of Khoy or Marand, further confirms its inclusion within the territory of Nakhchivan. Likewise, the western boundaries of Nakhchivan also encompassed the city of Dvin. According to the Arab geographer Yaqut al-Hamawi (1179–1229), Dvin was situated “in the province of Arran, on the distant frontiers of Azerbaijan.” Meanwhile, Abu Bakr al-Ahari noted that in 1338 the territories of Sharur and Dvin were governed by Hajibay, the son of the Ilkhanid amir Akənji [13, p. 81]. These accounts provide grounds for asserting that Dvin formed part of medieval Azerbaijan and, consequently, of Nakhchivan. According to Rashid al-Din Hamadani (1247–1318), the region of Qafan was also included within the Nakhchivan tumen during this period [9, p. 168; 13, pp. 81–82].

During this period, the Nakhchivan tumen included numerous settlements, fortresses, and defensive structures such as Vanand, Garabaghar, Giran, Julaha (modern Julfa), Shahbuz, Sharur, Alinja, Surmali, Garni, Taqmar, Fagnan, and others, as well as the Ashabi-Kahf Cave, the Khudaferin Bridges, and the Ziya al-Mulk Bridge [14, p. 97], many of which have survived to the present day.

Thü Socio-Political situation in Nakhchivan during the Ilkhanid Period. As noted above, following the third Mongol conquest of Azerbaijan in 1257, **Nakhchivan** was incorporated into the **Ilkhanate** in 1258. Prior to this, during the first half of the thirteenth century, the region had repeatedly been subjected to invasions by the Georgians, the Mongols, the Khwarazmshahs, and other occupying forces, while in certain periods it was governed by the Khwarazmshahs and the Mongols. Thus, from the final years of the **Atabegs of Azerbaijan** until the conquest of the region by the Ilkhanids, Nakhchivan had already faced considerable hardships, and the political, economic, and cultural achievements attained during the twelfth century had declined under the destructive impact of invading powers. Its significant military-strategic position made the region a constant target during these years. The repeated transfer of authority from one power to another substantially intensified political instability in the region, which in turn hindered the development of economic and cultural life.

The state established by Hulagu Khan was not confined solely to the territories of the Atabegs of Azerbaijan but extended over much broader lands. During the initial years of his rule, Hulagu Khan conquered a number of states and consolidated his authority within these territories. In addition to Azerbaijan, the empire created by Hulagu Khan in the Near East included Iraq-i Arab, Iraq-i Ajam, Kirman, Georgia, Asia Minor (Rum), Kurdistan, Fars, Khuzistan, Khorasan, and several other regions [12, p. 15].

The formation of the Ilkhanid state, the transformation of Azerbaijan into the central province of this political entity, and the advantages associated with this status constituted the principal causes of the prolonged wars between the Golden Horde and the Ilkhanids, driven by the Golden Horde khans' claims over Azerbaijan. During the campaigns of the Golden Horde, Azerbaijani territories were devastated by invading forces, the population was plundered, and severe damage was inflicted upon the economy. In 1263, 1265, 1288, 1290, and subsequent years, they launched expeditions into the northern provinces of the state. During these campaigns, several Azerbaijani regions, including Nakhchivan, became battlefields [19, pp. 69–70]. Concerning this matter, the academician Alasgar Alizade observed that during this period the region suffered not only from land and taxation policies but even more from the destruction caused by the conflicts between the Ilkhanids and the Golden Horde [21, p. 90].

Following the death of Hulagu Khan, internal conflicts emerged and gradually intensified among the nomadic feudal lords and financial officials. In the early years of the state's formation, a certain degree of common interest had existed among the nomadic feudal elites. However, later - particularly toward the end of

the reign of Abaqa Khan (1265–1282) - after princes and emirs had consolidated their authority and influence within the territories entrusted to them, the former unity among the nomadic feudal lords began to disintegrate. They united in factions led by princes and prominent emirs and engaged in struggles against one another. Over time, this rivalry lost its concealed character and assumed an open and overt form.

The nomadic feudal lords and emirs, who possessed extensive authority, played a decisive role in the feudal internecine struggles conducted under the pretext of preserving the hereditary principle of succession to the Ilkhanid throne. Large feudal landholders and emirs, relying upon the principle of dynastic succession, constantly competed with one another and frequently engaged in bloody conflicts. The principal cause of this struggle was the concentration of lands in the hands of the nobility, the revenues derived from these lands, and the increasing economic and political power of major feudal lords resulting from the ruthless exploitation of the population [1, p. 259].

After Abaqa Khan, power passed to Ahmad Tekuder (1282-1284). However, he was soon deposed through the efforts of dissatisfied feudal groups, and Arghun Khan (1284-1291) ascended the throne. During Arghun Khan's reign, feudal wars intensified even further. The struggle against the central authority, led by Amir Nawruz, continued for an extended period. Following Arghun Khan's death in 1291, severe disputes arose over the selection of a new Ilkhan. Ghaykhatu (1291-1295), the son of Abaqa Khan, emerged victorious from these internecine conflicts and was proclaimed Ilkhan. Nevertheless, he quickly became a mere instrument in the hands of rival feudal factions. The governors of several provinces rose against him. Consequently, the central state apparatus weakened and lost its capacity to suppress opposition forces effectively. In 1295, two Ilkhans were replaced in Azerbaijan within the same year. With the support of powerful feudal factions, Baydu was proclaimed Ilkhan in place of Ghaykhatu. Yet only a few months later he was removed from power, and Ghazan Khan (1295-1304) was proclaimed ruler of the Ilkhanid state in Qarabagh [2, pp. 21-22].

Following the death of Hulagu Khan (1258-1265), the struggles among Mongol princes competing for the throne once again transformed Nakhchivan into one of the principal centers of political developments, as had been the case in earlier periods [15, p. 35]. During the reigns of the Mongol rulers Abaqa Khan, Ahmad Tekuder, Arghun Khan, Ghaykhatu, and Baydu, Nakhchivan, like other Azerbaijani regions, remained politically fragmented [6, p. 82]. During the 1290s, when internal conflicts intensified, Nakhchivan became a refuge for opposition forces. In 1294, the Mongol prince Anbarji, who sought to escape persecution, was killed near Nakhchivan, where he had fled in search of protection. Shortly thereafter, the struggle for the throne between Ghaykhatu and Baydu ended in 1295 with the victory of the latter [10, p. 230]. Baydu Khan's seizure of power following his victory over Ghaykhatu greatly alarmed another Mongol prince, Ghazan Khan. Ghazan dispatched troops under the command of his generals Amir Nawruz and Qutluq against Baydu. At

that time, Baydu Khan fled to Nakhchivan in search of protection. It is evident that his intention was to seek refuge in Alinja Castle. Upon learning of this, Ghazan Khan sent his military forces to Nakhchivan in pursuit of Baydu. During these events, Baydu Khan's military commanders - Choban, Toqachar, Qurumishi, and several of his close associates - abandoned him and defected to Ghazan Khan's side. In such circumstances, the weakened Baydu Khan was captured by Ghazan's forces and brought to Tabriz, where he was executed in Baği-Neykəş [24, p. 168; 6, p. 83; 15, p. 35]. After Baydu Khan's death, the accession of Ghazan Khan in 1295 ushered in a period of relative stability within the Ilkhanate, accompanied by certain advances in the economic and cultural spheres. During this period, Nakhchivan, like other Azerbaijani regions, came under Ghazan Khan's authority. In the autumn of 1301, upon returning from his Egyptian campaign, Ghazan Khan visited Nakhchivan and from there proceeded to Arran [24, p. 193; 15, p. 35].

The elimination of the destruction inflicted upon the Nakhchivan region during previous years, as well as various reconstruction activities - including the restoration of Alinja Castle - were carried out primarily during the reform era initiated by Ghazan Khan. It should be noted that, in order to restore the former strength of the Ilkhanid state, Ghazan Khan was compelled to fundamentally alter the direction of domestic policy and implement a number of significant reforms. The decrees issued by Ghazan Khan in connection with the reforms carried out between 1297 and 1304 were distinguished by their sophistication and importance from socio-political, socio-economic, religious, and legal perspectives alike. The foundation of his reforms consisted of laws concerning the adoption and consolidation of Islam, military organization and troop maintenance, economic administration, land and peasant rights, commercial and financial regulations, palace administration, the observance of internal order, judicial procedures, and property rights [8].

As previously noted, the reforms implemented by Ghazan Khan proved significant not only for other Azerbaijani regions but also for Nakhchivan. Thus, according to a decree issued by Ghazan Khan in 1303, landowners were granted the right to return peasants who had fled their places of residence within a period of thirty years [2, p. 51]. This policy had a positive effect on demographic growth in the Nakhchivan region. As a consequence of this demographic increase, whereas in the 1240s the city of Nakhchivan paid an annual tribute of 113,000 dinars (11 *tümens* and 3,000 dinars) to the treasury, by the beginning of the fourteenth century this amount had risen to 150,000 dinars annually [15, p. 46; 10, p. 230]. Naturally, the various districts of Nakhchivan were not exempt from such obligations: Ordubad generated an annual income of 2 million 600 thousand dinars, while Azad, despite being a small town, participated in tax payments through its production of grain crops, cotton, and grapes [14, p. 99; 10, p. 230].

Although the Mongol taxation system was based upon the earlier Seljuk experience in this sphere, it was considerably heavier in scale. The imposition of more

than thirty-seven different taxes and duties, including the principal taxes such as *kalan*, *qopchur* (known in Nakhchivan as *kanqçur* or *qoyunhaqla*), and *tamgha*, impoverished the population. The extensive nature of these taxes and obligations is reflected even more clearly in the registers documenting the Ilkhanids' financial affairs, imports and exports, and taxation system. All of these factors negatively affected the political stability of the population. Owing to the burden of taxation, the inhabitants of Nakhchivan, Marand, and Sarab complained that tax collectors and officials ignored Ghazan Khan's decrees, confiscated goods at will, collected taxes exceeding the prescribed amounts, and "demanded 20 dinars instead of one dinar" [2, p. 54].

One of the principal indicators of the political significance of the Nakhchivan region for the Mongols during the Ilkhanid period was the minting of Ilkhanid coins there. Following Ghazan Khan's monetary reform of 1303, one of the seventy-five mints established throughout the Ilkhanid state was founded in Nakhchivan [26, p. 137]. In the medieval period, mints were generally established in cities that could be securely defended by the state. Since the Nakhchivan region held considerable political importance for the Ilkhanids, mints operated there and coinage was produced. Coins bearing the names of Ilkhanid rulers such as Abu Sa'id Bahadur Khan (1316-1335), Arpa Ke'un (1335-1336), Muhammad Khan (1336-1338), Sati Beg (1338-1339), Suleiman Khan (1339-1344), and Anushiravan were minted in the city of Nakhchivan. During the reign of Abu Sa'id, the first gold coin was struck in Nakhchivan in 1333, weighing approximately 3.35 grams. In the same year, silver dirhams weighing 1.40 grams were also minted. During the brief reign of Arpa Khan, copper coins were likewise issued. Numismatic evidence confirms that coins were minted in Nakhchivan in 1336, 1338, 1347, 1350, 1353, and 1356 [6, p. 87]. Among the nineteen Azerbaijani cities possessing mints during the Ilkhanid period, alongside renowned urban centers such as Baku, Tabriz, Maragha, Sultaniyya, Salmas, and Shabran, the inclusion of the city of Nakhchivan (1244-1245; 1333-1334), as well as regional settlements such as Sharur (1349-1350; 1351-1352), Alinja, and Andijan [5, p. 166], demonstrates the political significance of this region for statehood, together with its geopolitical and administrative influence. In sources relating to the period under discussion, alongside the name Nakhchivan, the settlements of Sharur and Alinja are also mentioned with increasing frequency [18, pp. 16, 23]. One particularly noteworthy aspect is that this process was not confined solely to the city of Nakhchivan but extended to other urban centers incorporated into the administration of the region as a whole. The location of these towns along the trade route known at the time as the "Nakhchivan Road" also played a significant role in this development. The fact that in 1305-1306 Oljeitu (Muhammad Khudabanda) traveled from the direction of Maragha to winter quarters in Mughan and Arran specifically via the Nakhchivan Road [2, p. 35] demonstrates that this route was considered more active and reliable [10, p. 231].

The reforms implemented by Ghazan Khan played a major role in the socio-political life of the Ilkhanate. The implementation of certain aspects of these reforms paved the way for a transformation among the Mongols from a nomadic and destructive mentality toward a more settled culture, and from paganism to monotheism - namely Islam. Ghazan Khan's religious reforms exercised an undeniable influence not only within the Ilkhanid state but also upon Mongol culture in general. It should be noted that during the initial stages of Mongol rule, paganism and Christianity were favored in the conquered territories. Chormaqan Noyan even patronized Christianity and permitted the construction of churches in Tabriz and Nakhchivan. According to Zeki Velidi Togan, this policy stemmed from his pagan beliefs and his warfare against Muslims [20, p. 260]. Ghazan Khan's conversion to Islam, his adoption of the name "Mahmud," and the foundation of the city of Mahmudabad generated sympathy among the local population toward the Ilkhanids. The religious reforms he implemented weakened the positions of paganism, Christianity, and other religions in Azerbaijan. Alongside the destruction of earlier pagan temples, churches and synagogues were also demolished, and mosques, khanqahs, and other Islamic monuments were erected in their place [15, pp. 17-18]. From this period onward, the construction of Muslim places of worship - particularly mosques - expanded significantly. It was precisely during this era that some of the finest and most magnificent examples of Azerbaijani architecture in Nakhchivan, including mosques and mausoleums, were constructed. Among the surviving monuments that continue to be venerated by local inhabitants and pilgrims from surrounding regions are the Pir Mosque in the village of Nüsünüs and the Juma Mosque in the village of Vənənd within the Ordubad District [16, p. 311]. Thus, the process of Islamization among the Mongols, initiated under Ahmad Tekuder, was effectively completed through the reforms carried out during the reign of Ghazan Khan (1295-1304).

The principal initiator and executor of Ghazan Khan's reforms was the chief vizier, physician, and renowned historian of the age, Rashid al-Din Hamadani. Having served as a physician at the court of Abaqa Khan, he gained proximity to the Mongol dynasty and eventually rose to the position of vizier under Ghazan Khan. He also acted as an intermediary in the economic and political relations between the Ilkhanid state and several other countries, including India [10, p. 231]. During Ghazan Khan's reign, educated and capable individuals were increasingly appointed to positions within the state administration, among whom notable figures from Azerbaijan, including Nakhchivan, occupied prominent places. These included the distinguished jurist Qavam al-Din Nakhchivani, Badr al-Din Muhammad Dizbeyi Nakhchivani [25, p. 35], Nasir al-Din al-Tusi, and others. Among them, Shams al-Din Juvayni, while holding a high-ranking office at the Ilkhanid court, maintained close ties with Nakhchivan and secured a decree from the Ilkhanid ruler between 1263 and 1284 concerning the operation of two madrasas intended to promote education there [17, p. 20]. The distinguished philosopher Najm al-Din Nakhchivani, the scholar and

thinker Hasan Nakhchivani, the physician and Sufi Kamal al-Din Nakhchivani, the famous jurist Qavam al-Din Nakhchivani, and others likewise left a profound mark on the history of their native Nakhchivan and contributed to its development [10, p. 232].

One of the principal factors behind the relative cultural and economic development achieved during Ghazan Khan's reign was the stabilization of the political situation in comparison with earlier years. Nevertheless, after Ghazan Khan's rule, the continuation of internal conflicts within the state once again hindered the cultural and economic development of the Nakhchivan region, while its significance as a refuge in difficult times re-emerged. The accession of the minor Abu Sa'id Bahadur Khan (1316-1335) to the throne in 1316 and the transformation of the chief emir Chupan into the de facto ruler of the state stimulated the intensification of feudal internecine warfare throughout the country.

Thus, in 1319, an uprising against the central authority broke out in Georgia, then part of the Ilkhanid state, under the leadership of Amir Qurumishi. After Emir Chupan achieved victory over Ozbeg Khan, he punished several emirs, including the governor of Georgia, Amir Qurumishi. Perceiving Chupan's actions as a personal insult, Qurumishi allied himself with the ruler of Diyarbakir, Irinj, and several other emirs, subsequently launching a rebellion against the central government [12, p. 21].

The rebels advanced from Georgia into Azerbaijan and proceeded as far as Tabriz. During this period, Nakhchivan became their principal stronghold. The insurgents carried out extensive plunder and devastation across Azerbaijani territory. Hamdallah Qazvini even wrote that, had it not been for divine assistance, the rebels would have fulfilled all their ambitions and nothing of the state's possessions would have remained [20, p. 70]. In Nakhchivan, they assembled an army and issued decrees in the name of Abu Sa'id, declaring that supporters of Amir Qurumishi and Amir Irinj were permitted to kill any adherents of the Chobanids they captured. They also dispatched envoys to Abu Sa'id, alleging that Emir Chupan failed to obey the ruler's orders and decrees, and demanded that the sultan surrender Chupan [12, p. 21]. Evidently, during the uprising the rebellious feudal lords concentrated their forces precisely in Nakhchivan, from where they launched an attack against the sultan. In the bloody battle that took place in the Zangezour region, Abu Sa'id managed with difficulty to suppress the rebellion and, owing to his personal bravery, earned the title "Bahadur" [10, p. 232]. Nevertheless, the suppression of the revolt failed to stabilize the situation within the country completely. Following Abu Sa'id's death, political tensions became even more acute.

After his death in 1335, feudal warfare within the Ilkhanid state intensified dramatically. Hamdallah Qazvini wrote that during this period the long-anticipated turmoil finally erupted in the country: every notable of the state advanced his own claim, and each sought to place his own candidate upon the throne. The measures undertaken by Arpa Ke'un, who succeeded Abu Sa'id, to strengthen central authority proved ineffective. The Oirat tribe, led by Amir Ali Padshah in

opposition to the central government, deposed Arpa Khan and proclaimed Musa Khan as Ilkhan in 1336. Soon afterward, however, he too was replaced by a new ruler, Muhammad Khan (1336-1338). During Muhammad Khan's reign, the struggle for power assumed a new form. Feudal factions were no longer competing merely to seize control of the unified Ilkhanid realm; rather, they began striving for independence within separate provinces and for complete liberation from Ilkhanid authority. Consequently, a condition of political fragmentation and multiple competing authorities emerged within the territories of the Ilkhanid state.

After Abu Sa'id, Shaykh Hasan gathered troops in Rum and advanced toward Tabriz. Upon learning of this, the Jalayirid Shaykh Hasan, together with Muhammad Khan, assembled forces and marched through Nakhchivan against the Chobanids. During the ensuing battle, Muhammad Khan was killed and Shaykh Hasan fled. Thereafter, Nakhchivan fell within the sphere of influence of the Chobanid feudal lords [15, p. 36].

Between 1336 and 1344, power in Azerbaijan changed hands eight times. The instability of the domestic situation also affected the country's external affairs. During this period, Azerbaijan was repeatedly subjected to invasions by the armies of the Golden Horde [12, p. 3]. These struggles likewise intensified the socio-political tensions within Nakhchivan.

Shaykh Hasan Chobani was assassinated in 1344. Upon hearing this news, the Chobanid emirs Malik Ashraf and Yaghi Basti postponed their Shiraz campaign and returned to Tabriz. At that time, Alaki Bahadur, one of the mamluks of Demirdash - the father of Shaykh Hasan - governed Nakhchivan and had effectively become an autonomous ruler there. He joined Malik Ashraf, thereby strengthening their military power. In the same year, another Chobanid emir, Surgan, escaped from the fortress of Qarahisar in Rum, where he had been imprisoned, assembled troops, and advanced toward Tabriz. Malik Ashraf and Yaghi Basti traveled to Nakhchivan under the pretext of confronting him, and the opposing forces met at Mamuriyya. During this period, Chobanid oppression spread widely throughout Azerbaijan. The Chobanid emir Malik Ashraf, notorious for his cruelty, amassed seventeen خزانن (treasuries) through tyranny and plunder [15, p. 36]. His oppression exhausted not only the lower strata of society but also landowners, merchants, and other groups. As elsewhere in Azerbaijan, Chobanid oppression in Nakhchivan generated widespread dissatisfaction among the population. Unable to endure these hardships, a portion of the inhabitants abandoned the country [15, p. 36]. Research conducted by Rauf Mammadov indicates that during Malik Ashraf's rule (1344-1356), wealthy groups in Nakhchivan sympathetic to the Jochids were forced to flee the region [6, p. 91]. During the reign of Jani Beg, the Golden Horde experienced considerable political and socio-economic development. Consequently, many notable individuals from Tabriz, Ardabil, Barda, Beylagan, and Nakhchivan escaped Malik Ashraf's oppression and sought refuge within the territories of the Golden Horde. They also appealed to

Jani Beg, urging him to seize power in Azerbaijan [19, pp. 74-75]. Shortly thereafter, pursued by Jani Beg, Malik Ashraf himself came to Nakhchivan - which remained under his authority - seeking refuge and placed his treasury, filled with accumulated wealth, in Alinja Castle [6, p. 91]. However, he was captured and executed in 1357 [2, p. 28]. Finally, in 1357, the rule of the Ilkhanid state came to an end. Like other Azerbaijani regions, Nakhchivan was conquered by Jani Beg and entrusted to the administration of his son, Birdi Beg.

As can be seen, the arrival of the Golden Horde was welcomed favorably by the local population not only in other regions of Azerbaijan but also in Nakhchivan. This attitude constituted an open expression of popular dissatisfaction with the oppression of the Chobanids. Although the Chobanids, who occupied a dominant position during the final years of the Ilkhanate, were unable to establish an independent state, they effectively governed the country in the name of the Ilkhanid rulers.

During the reigns of Hulagu Khan (1256-1265), Abaqa Khan (1265-1282), Ahmad Tekuder (1282-1284), Arghun Khan (1284-1291), Ghaykhatu (1291-1295), and Baydu (1295), particular attention was devoted to strengthening Nakhchivan strategically [3, p. 168]. In most cases, this policy stemmed from the necessity of securing defense amid internal conflicts and struggles for the throne. Although Ghazan Khan ensured stability and development throughout his nine-year reign, the prosperity of the Ilkhanid state did not endure for long after his death.

As noted above, Nakhchivan suffered severe destruction during the prolonged wars fought between the Ilkhanids and the Golden Horde in 1263, 1265, 1288, 1290, and 1318. The region was devastated, its settlements ruined, and large portions of its population were killed. At the same time, the Ilkhanids themselves launched campaigns against the Golden Horde between 1319 and 1325, suppressed the Sultaniyya uprising in 1334, and decisively repelled the invasion of the Golden Horde ruler Ozbeg Khan in 1335. Nevertheless, these represented the final successes of the disintegrating empire. Following the death of Abu Sa'id Bahadur Khan in 1335, authority formally remained in the hands of the Ilkhanids. In reality, however, within the territories of the Ilkhanid state - effectively governed by the Chobanids - the number of forces refusing to submit to central authority steadily increased. As a result, the defensive significance of Nakhchivan once again came to the forefront. The decisive influence exercised by the *kutvals* (fortress commanders) of Alinja Castle, including Uztemur [15, p. 31], played a crucial role in these developments. Consequently, throughout the struggles for power, Nakhchivan repeatedly emerged as a focal refuge for rival political forces.

Conclusion. The Mongol invasion carried out under the leadership of Hulagu Khan in the 1250s, together with the subsequent internal political struggles that unfolded within the territories incorporated into the Ilkhanate, left deep traces in history through the destruction of settlements and material-cultural monuments, as well as through the large-scale loss of human

life. Although the reforms implemented during the nine-year reign of Ghazan Khan (1295-1304) contributed to a certain degree of stability and development in Nakhchivan, the situation deteriorated once again after his rule owing to renewed internal conflicts and the oppression of the Chobanid emirs. During this period, rival claimants to the throne repeatedly selected Nakhchivan - strategically advantageous from a military perspective - as a place of refuge. As a consequence, the region became one of the principal centers of political events, which intensified the socio-political situation, hindered economic development, and simultaneously exposed a region that had flourished culturally in previous centuries to widespread devastation. The invading Mongol forces destroyed a number of the magnificent architectural monuments created by Ajami Abu Bakr Nakhchivani and his successors, many of which represented outstanding works of art and architecture. Most tragic of all was the fact that Nakhchivan, like other regions of Azerbaijan, suffered from the consequences of this destruction for a prolonged period. Agricultural lands, roads, and entire cities were devastated, and until these could be restored, the region's economic and cultural connections remained significantly weakened.

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